

THE MOLECULAR COMPOUNDS OF 4:6-DIBROMO-1:3-DINITROBENZENE*

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Molecular compounds of 4:6-dibromo-1:3-dinitrobenzene with α - and β -naphthols, α - and β -naphthylamines, naphthalene, acenaphthene, phenanthrene, pyridine and urotropine have been isolated. With naphthylamines, pyridine and urotropine condensation products have also been isolated.

Sudborough and Picton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 589) and later Jois and Manjunath (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 633) prepared molecular compounds of 4:6-dichloro-1:3-dinitrobenzene with α - and β -naphthylamines. In addition, the latter have isolated molecular compounds with naphthalene, α - and β -naphthols, benzidine and pyridine. In the present investigation molecular compounds of 4:6-dibromo-1:3-dinitrobenzene have been prepared with a view to studying how the introduction of two bromine atoms into *m*-dinitrobenzene influences the formation and stability of molecular compounds.

4:6-Dibromo-1:3-dinitrobenzene forms molecular compounds with α - and β -naphthols, α - and β -naphthylamines, naphthalene and pyridine. In addition, molecular compounds with acenaphthene, phenanthrene and urotropine have been isolated. All the molecular compounds except those of pyridine and urotropine possess deep colour. The molecular ratio is 1:1 except with pyridine and urotropine. Two molecules of pyridine unite with one molecule of the nitro compound to form a dipyridonium salt (*cf.* Jois and Manjunath, *J. Mysore Univ.*, 1932, 6, 13) of the following structure:—

The molecular compound with urotropine, on the other hand, contains two molecular proportions of the nitro compound with one of urotropine. Dimethylariline, diphenylamine and quinoline give only red solutions but molecular compounds could not be isolated. Anthracene, fluorene, diphenyl, *p*-toluidine, benzidine, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroanilines do not give any indication of the formation of molecular compounds. With benzidine condensation takes place readily and molecular compound could not be isolated in a pure state. As Buehler (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 1941) puts it, molecular compounds are probably intermediates in the formation of condensation products.

The molecular compounds of 4:6-dichloro-1:3-dinitrobenzene appear to be more stable and more easily formed than the corresponding compounds with 4:6-dibromo-1:3-dinitrobenzene. Similar observation is made by Buehler (*loc. cit.*) with molecular compounds of 2:4-dinitrochlorobenzene and the corresponding bromo derivative.

4:6-Dibromo-1:3-dinitrobenzene, required for this investigation, is prepared starting with acetanilide which is converted into *m*-dibromobenzene by modifying the method of Jackson and Cohoe (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1901, 26, 3). *m*-Dibromobenzene is then nitrated to yield mostly 4:6-dibromo-1:3-dinitrobenzene according to the method of Nietzki and Shelder as modified by Jois and Manjunath (*J. Mysore Univ.*, 1930, 4, 239).

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EXPERIMENTAL

The molecular compounds except these of pyridine and urotropine were prepared by dissolving the two components in molecular proportions separately in a suitable solvent and mixing the hot solutions. On cooling, crystals separated and were recrystallised from the same solvent. The molecular compound with pyridine was prepared and purified in the same manner as was adopted by Jois and Manjunath (*loc. cit.*) in the preparation of the molecular compound of pyridine and 4:6-dichloro-1:3-dinitrobenzene. To prepare the molecular compound with urotropine the two components in the proper proportion were dissolved in dry acetone, mixed and set aside for some days, when a mixture of the condensation product and the molecular compound separated. From this mixture a pure sample of the molecular compound was obtained by dissolving in methyl alcohol and precipitating with ether. The other details regarding the molecular compounds are given in Table I.

Condensation Products

Condensation Product of (A) with α -Naphthylamine: 2:4-Dinitro-5-bromophenyl- α -naphthylamine.—When the molecular compound (3) was dissolved in alcohol and refluxed for about 1/2 hour, the condensation product gradually separated. This is found to exist in two modifications, yellow and red. The former was obtained by crystallising the crude condensation product from benzene, xylene or ethyl acetate and the latter by refluxing the benzene solution and allowing it to cool. The yellow form was also obtained directly by refluxing the components in molecular ratio in alcoholic solution, m.p. 191-92°, red variety, m.p. 191-92° and its melting point was not lowered when mixed with the yellow form. [Found (yellow form): Br, 20.5; (red form): Br, 20.8. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4N_2$, Br requires Br, 20.6 per cent).

Condensation product of (A) with β -Naphthylamine: 2:4-Dinitro-5-bromophenyl- β -naphthylamine.—This was formed readily on heating a solution of the molecular compound (4) in alcohol and was found to exist in two forms, orange and red. The former was obtained by crystallising the crude condensation product from ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol or better from acetone and the latter from benzene. The red variety changes over to the orange variety slowly on keeping, rapidly on heating to 110-115°. Both the varieties melt at 192-93° and the melting point is not lowered by mixing the two. [Found (orange form): Br, 20.6, (yellow form): Br 20.8. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4N_2$, Br requires Br, 20.6 per cent]. The orange or red variety gives intense red colour with concentrated sulphuric acid, while the corresponding condensation product of α -naphthylamine develops an intense bluish green colour.

Condensation product of (A) with Pyridine.—The molecular compound (3) on heating either alone or with water changes over to the condensation product with elimination of hydrogen bromide. It is best prepared by heating pyridine (2 mols.) with 4:6-dibromo-1:3-dinitrobenzene (1 mol.) for some time on the water-bath and then boiling with water for a few hours. It is crystallised from boiling water as golden yellow needles. It does not melt but decomposes with explosive violence at about 340°. [Found: N, 17.6. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4N_4$, requires N, 17.4 per cent).

Condensation product of (A) with Urotropine.—The yellow residue that separated from the molecular compound (6) was washed repeatedly with hot methyl alcohol and then crystallised from boiling acetone in which it is sparingly soluble, when yellow crystals were obtained. It is very sparingly soluble in water and in the ordinary organic solvents, and melts with decomposition at 201-202°. (Found: N, 17·6; Br, 25·5. $C_{18}H_{14}O_8N_4Br_2$ requires N, 17·8; Br, 25·4 per cent).

TABLE I

Molecular Compounds of 4:6-dibromo 1:3-dinitrobenzene (A) with (B)

No.	B	Molecular ratio A:B	Solvent used.	Form of the compound.	M.p.	Molecular formula.	Analysis	
							Calc.	Found.
1	α -Naphthol	1:1	CCl_4	Yellow prismatic crystals.	91-92°	$C_{16}H_{10}O_2N_2Br_2$	Br, 34·0	Br, 34·1
2	β -Naphthol	1:1	Do	Orange-yellow prismatic crystals.	83-84°	$C_{16}H_{10}O_2N_2Br_2$	Br, 34·0	Br, 34·3
3	α -Naphthylamine.	1:1	Do.	Dark-red prismatic crystals.	80-80·5°	$C_{16}H_{11}O_2N_3Br_2$	Br, 34·1	Br, 34·3
*4	β -Naphthylamine.	1:1	Ligroin	Chocolate-red prismatic needles.	61·5-62·5°	$C_{16}H_{11}O_2N_3Br_2$	Br, 34·1	Br, 34·4
**5	Pyridine	1:2	(same method as described by Jois and Manjunath, <i>loc. cit.</i>)	Colourless micro-crystalline.	...	$C_{19}H_{13}O_4N_4Br_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	N, 10·8 Br, 30·8	N, 10·5 Br, 30·8
†6	Urotropine	2:1	Acetone	Colourless needles.	...	$C_{19}H_{16}O_8N_4Br_4 \cdot 4H_2O$	Br, 37·0	Br, 37·0
††7	Naphthalene	1:1	Absolute alcohol	Lemon-yellow crystals	66-67°	$C_{18}H_{10}O_2N_2Br_2$	Br, 35·2	Br, 35·5
‡8	Phenanthrene.	1:1	Do.	Yellow needles.	66·5°	$C_{19}H_{11}O_2N_2Br_2$	Br, 31·7	Br, 31·5
‡‡9	Acenaphthene	1:1	Do.	Deep-yellow needles	58-60°	$C_{18}H_{11}O_2N_2Br_2$	Br, 33·3	Br, 33·6

* Ether or CCl_4 gives only condensation product. The molecular compound changes to the condensation product on keeping even at the room temperature

** The compound is soluble in alcohol and water but insoluble in ether and benzene. It ionises in aqueous solution and gives precipitate with silver nitrate solution. On heating it gradually changes to the yellow compound decomposing at 165°.

† Soluble in water, ionises in aq. soln. and gives a precipitate with silver nitrate. On heating the compound changes to a yellow product m.p. with decomp. at 201-202°.

†† The compound is not stable in the hot.

‡ The compound turns orange on keeping for some days.

‡‡ On exposure, colour deepens to brown.